

Novel Experimental Techniques to Determine Fracture Toughness of Cellular Foam and Sea Water Effects

D. Penumadu¹, Y. J. Weitsman², A. Siriruk³, K. G. Thomas⁴
¹Professor and JIAM Chair of Excellence, ²Emeritus Professor,
³Graduate Student, ⁴Supervisor for Mechanical and Electrical Shop
Civil and Environmental Engineering, 223 Perkins Hall
University of Tennessee, Knoxville, USA
dpenumad@utk.edu

SUMMARY

A new experimental setup has been developed that can measure mode-I fracture toughness of foam core material for sandwich composites with controlled crack growth that is channelled along the mid plane. The effect of long-term exposure to sea water on fracture toughness for PVC foam is reported. This overcomes the cracks tendency to deflect towards the facing which has been a problem encountered by previous investigators. Techniques and initial results to obtain multi-axial or mixed mode fracture behavior by the application of tension and/or torsion on flat, pre-cracked foam samples are presented. These techniques employ a custom made loading mechanism and specially designed specimens.

Keywords: PVC Foam, naval applications, sea water effect, Energy Release Rate

INTRODUCTION

Stitched cross ply carbon fiber and vinyl ester resin based polymeric composites (facings) and sandwich structures (with PVC foam core) are utilized in naval craft and thereby are exposed to both sea water environment and large temperature variations over extended periods. The coupled effect of configurational distortions due to sea water exposure and combined effect from freezing and its cycling must be considered in the design. The experimental data presented in this paper is first of its kind in developing basic science on the effect of prolonged exposure to sea water on the fracture behavior of closed cellular foam. The objective of our ongoing research is to evaluate the combined effects of harsh naval environment (sea water and low temperature) on the mechanical properties of carbon fiber and vinyl ester resin based polymeric composites and sandwich structures. Important fundamental understanding on the effects of long term exposure to seawater, subsequent freezing, and freeze/thaw effects on material properties (G, E) of PVC foam core, including fracture toughness, and interfacial delamination toughness are being evaluated as a part of this research.

FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF CELLULAR FOAM

Fracture toughness of polymeric foam was evaluated in the past by using hinges glued

to the facings in either a Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) or a Tilted Sandwich Debond (TSD) device. Using such methods, the effect of exposure to sea water on fracture toughness was investigated by pre-soaking of the specimens for target duration in simulated sea water at a controlled temperature of 40 °C in the water bath prior to the initial delamination testing. Subsequently the specimens were soaked for interim periods of two weeks during intermittent crack growth between unloading and reloading cycles.

However, these types of testing configurations deflect the growing crack away from the initial pre-cracked plane towards the facing-core interface, thus rendering the fracture process to become random and highly intractable. This presented a significant obstacle for interpreting data reported in currently available literature.

To overcome the existing limitation, the fracture toughness of foams was investigated by employing a double cantilevered sandwich specimens with notches on both sides to successfully control the direction of crack growth. This overcomes the crack's tendency to deflect towards the facing which has been a problem encountered by previous investigators.

Mixed mode fracture behavior of foam materials is being evaluated by applying loads to tilted double cantilever beams, and combine tension and torsion on flat, pre-cracked foam specimens employing a custom made loading mechanism and specially designed samples.

MATERIALS

Composite sandwich panels of size 60 x 90 cm (2 x 3 ft) and 2.54 cm (1.0 in) thickness were fabricated using the VARTM process. The facing material was made of carbon stitch bonded fabric designated by LT650- C10-R2VE supplied by the Devold AMT AS, Sweden. This was an equibiaxial fabric produced using Toray's T700 12k carbon fiber tow with a vinyl ester compatible sizing. The matrix used was Dow Chemical's DERAKANE 510A-40, a brominated vinyl ester, formulated for the VARTM process. The bromination imparts a fire-resistant property to the composite. The core material was H100 Divynicel PVC foam having an average density of 100 kg/m³ and average cell size of 0.15 mm.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Several test apparatuses and test specimens were adapted for the testing of foam properties and core/facings interfacial debonding. Various test results, confirm that the experimental procedures implemented herein provide high quality test data. In view of its low modulus of foam, it was necessary to employ small amplitude load cells and a special mechanism for load introduction through interfacial shear alone. The tensile test setup is shown in Figure 1, sample locations within the foam are sketched in Figure 2, with sample geometry and torsional test setup shown in Figure 3.

Figure 1: A tension/torsion MTS machine (a) with custom made grips (b) and foam test samples (c).

Figure 2: Foam core sheet (25 mm) and specimen layers

Figure 3: Specimen geometry, tensile and torsional testing on foam

Modulus Variation Through Thickness

Tensile measurements indicated that the stiffness of 25.4 mm H100 plates varies across their thickness. This variability was recorded for specimens having a thickness of 4 mm cut from various locations as shown in Figure 2, establishing the presence of a consistent, gradual increase in Young's modulus towards the center of the foam core. A typical variation of Young's Modulus is listed in Table 1 and Shear Modulus in Table 2, all for dry specimens.

Table 1: Values of the tensile E (in MPa) at the dry state for each 4 mm thick layer cut from four panels at room temperature for H 100 PVC foam

Sample layer	Top	Intermediate	Center	Intermediate	Bottom
E (MPa)	67.7	72.2	73.6	70.2	69.4

Table 2: Values of the Shear Modulus G (in MPa) at Room Temperature, dry (obtained from torsional tests)

Sample layer	AI	AII	BI	BII
1	25.73	24.99	23.15	23.86
2	27.88	27.49	27.74	26.33
3	28.81	28.92	28.41	27.94
4	27.20	27.56	27.69	28.40
5	27.06	27.71	26.55	24.61

Exposure to sea ambience induces environmental effects into both polymeric facings and polymeric foams. It was established in earlier works that the ingress of sea water is essentially confined to the outer, exposed, facing of the sandwich structure and to just a few adjacent cells of the foam core^{1,2}. Several experiments on foam samples obtained from the same location along the thickness were soaked in sea water at 40 °C for extended periods of time and the above tests were repeated to evaluate the effect on modulus values. As noted earlier, the ingress of sea water into polymeric closed cell foam is confined to the near vicinity of the exposed boundaries, thus the major portions of the test samples remained dry after exposure and no significant effect could be detected under tensile loading. Unlike the circumstance of tension, torsional loading data are much more sensitive to the presence of fluids, since in this case maximal shear strains occur near the outer boundaries of the test sample- where most of the fluid is indeed located. It was found that sea water consequently caused an overall degradation of 5% to 15% in the torsional response, which corresponds to a reduction in the shear modulus of the saturated region by up to 70%^{7,8}.

Delamination Toughness of Sandwich

Sandwich samples were loaded according to the set-up shown in Figure 4. Loading was introduced by means of an MTS servo-hydraulic 22 kN capacity testing machine under displacement control at a crosshead rate of 2 mm/min. A very precise smaller load cell with a full scale capacity of 0.44 kN was used to perform the carefully controlled delamination testing. Specimens were tested in either dry or “wet” states. The latter state was obtained under immersion for two to three weeks intermittent durations. Loads were monotonically increased under displacement control until noting an abrupt drop in their amplitudes, at which stage crack extensions were observed. At that point the crosshead displacement was programmed to stop, and machine to unload to zero displacement. The above loading-unloading procedure was repeated at each new crack length until total separation of the upper facing. The setup affords most accurate observations of crack tip positions on both sides of the delaminating specimen and a nearly definitive determination of load levels at the onset of intermittent crack growth by means of digital imaging. Using digital image analysis software (ImagePro®), crack morphology was also determined for use in calculating energy release rate values. This was done by focusing on the region of crack-tip and transferring the gray scale image to binary form using thresholding technique. The exact length of crack was obtained by tracking the number of pixels and conversion to length units using a known optical magnification at which digital images were obtained. In addition to observing crack propagation along the front of the specimen, the advancing cracks were also captured digitally along the back of the specimen with the aid of a highly polished mirror.

As noted above, it was necessary to re-soak each “wet” specimen for at least two to three weeks, in order to maintain a fully saturated crack tip region after each unloading and prior to each reloading. The digital images of the interfacial cracks that were also obtained during testing.

The resistance to delamination growth can be characterized by the strain energy release rate (G), where the critical energy release rate (G_c) is used as a measure of the interlaminar fracture toughness. Assuming a linear elastic response, it was chosen to determine the critical strain energy release rates by means of the “area method”. The area under each load/unload cycle was calculated numerically using the trapezoidal rule. Critical energy release rate, which defines the fracture toughness, was obtained using the equation 1 below:

$$G_c = \frac{1}{b} \cdot \frac{\Delta U}{\Delta a} \quad (1)$$

Where ΔU is the area under the load-displacement trace as the crack grows; Δa is the extended crack length noted during the test, and b is the width of specimen. The value calculated is the average energy consumed for the crack extension Δa . Typical experimental results are shown in Figure 5.

Experimental values of wet and dry interlaminar fracture toughness G_c , including data scatter and percent reduction caused by exposure to sea water are shown in Table 3 showing large reduction for interface (between facing and foam) fracture properties due to sea water exposure.

Figure 4: Delamination testing setup using a 0.44 kN load cell and sandwich specimen

Figure 5: Typical experimental data for an intermittent growth of a delamination crack

Table 3: Sea Water Effect on Delamination Toughness

	G_C (Front) Lower & Upper limit (N/m^2)	G_C (Back) Lower & Upper limit (N/m^2)	Representative Range (>50%) (N/m^2)
Dry	580-952	541-963	780-890
Wet	432-619	451-632	522-588
% Reduction	25-35%	17%-34%	33-34%

Dry and Wet Mode I Foam Fracture Toughness

H100 foam specimens were cut and machined to dimensions of 250 mm in length, 25 mm in width and 25 mm in height. To maintain a straight crack front, all specimens were machined to have equal V-notches along both sides at the middle of their height dimension. Aluminum T-bars were adhesively bonded to the top and bottom of all samples to reduce bending. A V-shaped sharp pre-crack was cut 25 mm away from the loaded edge. The experimental set-up is shown in Figure 6. The experiments were conducted at the rate of 1 mm/min.

Values of G_c were computed from load/unload data akin to those shown in Figure 5 for both dry and “wet” samples. It was necessary to reimmerse each “wet” sample in sea water for two weeks before its subsequent re-loading so as to maintain a wet crack-tip region. Results are tabulated in Table 4 indicating a certain increase (10 to 15%) in foam fracture toughness for PVC foam when subjected to long term exposure to sea water. This implies that water enhanced foam wall ductility, which agrees with microstructural features of cellular foam subjected to long term sea water exposure.

Figure 6: Foam fracture test setup using channeled section

Table 4: Dry and wet experimental results of foam fracture toughness G_c

Condition	Average G_c (Front)	Average G_c (Back)
	(N/m ²)	(N/m ²)
Dry (6 specimens, 7-9 cycles each)	844	829
Dry (Std. Dev.)	309	213
Wet (2 specimens, 7 cycles each)	938	964
Wet (Std. Dev.)	129	184

An Alternate Approach to Foam Fracture Toughness

The H100 Divynicel PVC foam specimen were cut and machined to have geometry as shown in Figure 3. The custom made tensile/torsional fixtures presented earlier were used with a given pre-cracked length in the mid height of the specimen to perform a fracture test. An external LVDT was attached to obtain accurate displacement data and an external 100lb sensitive load cell was also used. For several samples, preliminary tests were performed up to stress levels well below yield in the absence of an edge crack. Three cycles of load-unload were applied to ensure high repeatability of the elastic behavior of the specimen. Subsequently, a sharp edge crack was cut into the mid section of each of the above samples. Loads were monotonically increased under displacement control until noting an abrupt drop in their amplitudes, at which stage an unstable crack growth was observed spanning across the entire width of the specimens. Typical data under tensile loading are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Tensile fracture test results for samples with and without edge crack. The four straight upper lines account for the behavior of the uncracked specimens, while the other four are related to the response of the corresponding cracked samples.

Our ongoing research concerns the analysis of the data shown above to obtain fracture properties evaluated using the concept of "tearing energy" [9].

CONCLUSIONS

Long term exposure to sea water of sandwich structures consisting of polymeric composite facings and PVC foam core show substantial degradation (about 30 %) in the interfacial fracture toughness while at the same time an increase of about 10 % in the fracture toughness of the foam itself.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is supported by contract N00014-07-1-0504 from the Office of Naval Research (ONR), under a program managed by Dr. Yapa Rajapakse.

References

- 1 Li, X. and Weitsman, Y.J. Sea Water Effects on Foam Cored Composite Sandwich Layups. *Composite Part B.*, 2004, Vol.35 pp.451-459.
- 2 Ionita, A., and Weitsman, Y.J. A Model for Fluid Ingress in Polymeric Closed Cell Foams. *Mechanics of Materials.*, 2007, Vol.39 pp.434-444.
- 3 ASTM C 273/C 273M, Standard Test Method for Shear Properties of Sandwich Core Materials.
- 4 Penumadu, D., Weitsman, Y.J., and Siriruk, A. (2007): "Effect of Sea Water on Interfacial Delamination Behavior of Sandwich Layups." 16th International Conference on Composite Materials, July 8 – 13, Kyoto, Japan.
- 5 Weitsman, Y.J., Siriruk, A., and Penumadu, D. (2007): "Sea Water Effects on Polymeric Composites." 16th International Conference on Composite Materials, July 8 – 13, Kyoto, Japan.
- 6 Shivakumar, K.N., Swaminathan, G., and Sharpe, M. (2006). "Carbon/Vinyl Ester Composites for Enhanced Performance in Marine Applications." *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* 25, no. 10 (July 1): 1101-1116. doi:10.1177/0731684406065194.
- 7 Siriruk, A., Weitsman, J., and Penumadu, D. (2008): "Polymeric foams and sandwich composites: Material properties, environmental effects, and shear-lag modeling." *Composites Science and Technology*, CSTE 3990, doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.02.034.
- 8 Siriruk, A., Penumadu, D., and Weitsman, Y.J. (2008): "Effect of sea environment on interfacial delamination behavior of polymeric sandwich structures." *Composites Science and Technology*, CSTE 3990, doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.02.033.
- 9 Oh, H.L. (1976): "A simple Method for Measuring Tearing Energy of Nicked Rubber Strips." *Mechanics of Crack Growth, ASTM STP 590, American Society for testing and Materials*, pp. 104-114.